

Case Examples

Project 24: Developing A Realtime Monitoring System and Program to Improve COVID-19 Testing for Latinx Populations

Partners: Brown University, Progreso Latino

Project 24 combined quantitative (e.g., modeling and GIS mapping) and qualitative methods (e.g., focus groups and interviews) to contextualize and intervene on barriers related to COVID-19 testing among Latinx populations in Rhode Island. Project 24 worked collaboratively with Progreso Latino, the largest community organization in the state working to serve Rhode Island's Latinx and immigrant communities. Project 24 relied on community-engaged, data-driven approaches to identify, locate, and map systemic barriers to COVID-19 testing among Latinx populations. The team then operationalized their findings by developing implementation strategies and creating culturally competent tools to directly address identified barriers to COVID-19.

Leverage health information exchange (HIE) systems and develop pathways for cross-sector data sharing:

HIEs enable the transfer of health data between all members of healthcare ecosystem. Rhode Island's HIE ("CurrentCare"), which is operated by the Rhode Island Quality Institute, supports access to health data anywhere care is delivered in Rhode Island (with patients' permission). This health information includes lab tests, details pertaining to hospital visits, medications, and any other health data needed to support treatment and management of patient care.¹⁰¹ Project 24 used available HIE data to identify COVID-19 hotspots at the census tract level. These data were used to study testing trends over time and identify "testing deserts" or areas with high positivity rates and low per capita testing sites/services. Interviewees noted that HIEs are very valuable assets for linking clinical data to public health and research.

Develop bi-directional communication platforms for community partners and members to share knowledge

and expertise: Project 24 worked with their community partner, Progreso Latino, to implement a series of focus groups with Latinx populations from testing deserts, as well as additional interviews with providers from participating community health centers who have large populations of Latinx patients. The focus groups and interviews were designed to elicit the relevant barriers to COVID-19 testing and to identify approaches to improve access to testing. These groups also helped inform promotora outreach strategies and the subsequent development of communication tools to further bridge testing access gaps. The focus groups served as a platform for community members to engage in bidirectional conversations about the pandemic with the Rhode Island Department of Health. Progreso Latino convened the focus groups and handled day-to-day logistics, while Project 24 team members provided technical and infrastructure support. Interviewees noted that the focus groups were crucial for understanding the community-specific barriers to testing access and also helped provide a platform for community members to voice concerns, ask questions, and speak directly to relevant stakeholders associated with the pandemic response in Rhode Island.

Build infrastructure to support the community health workforce:

The budget for this project was constructed to fully support the community organizations involved and foster opportunities for sustainable promotora engagement. For example, promotoras were employed on 2-year contracts, with the agreement that in the last 6 months of the contract the project would assist them with finding permanent employment. The promotoras worked as linkages between the community members and the health system partners, including three free clinics (Clínica Esperanza, Rhode Island Free Clinic, and Open Door Health) and three FQHCs (Providence Community Health Centers, Thundermist Health Centers, Blackstone Valley Community Health Center) in the state. Interviewees noted that promotoras helped in the "last quarter mile" by connecting community members with the health system through various engagement strategies. They also served as natural bridges for breaking down technical COVID-19 information into digestible formats for community members.

Project 37: New Jersey Healthcare Essential Worker Outreach and Education Study Testing Overlooked Occupation (NJ HEROES TOO)

Partners: ASPIRA Inc. of New Jersey; Central Jersey Family Health Consortium; Communities in Cooperation; East Orange Senior Volunteer Corporation; Health Coalition of Passaic County; Hillside Senior Recreation Center; Jazz4PCA; Mobile Family Success Center; New Brunswick Area Branch NAACP; New Brunswick Tomorrow; New Hope Baptist Church; Parker Health Group Inc.; Partnership for Maternal and Child Health of Northern New Jersey; Puerto Rican Action Board; Programs for Parents; Robert Wood Johnson University Hospital; Sister2Sister; The Bridge Inc.; United Way of Greater Union County; University Hospital Newark; Urban League of Union County Inc.; VNA Health Group

Project 37 tested different outreach strategies to implement noninvasive, home-based COVID-19 testing

in low-income, Black, and Latino communities in four New Jersey counties (see below) exhibiting high social vulnerability. Specifically, they explored the impact of community-based outreach and compared it with a workplace-based outreach approach focused on lower-income health care workers, essential support staff, their households, and their broader social networks. Drawing from long-established relationships and community partners, the team engaged 16 community organizations in the design, development, and implementation of this project. Key strategies include:

Use data tools to identify communities experiencing the greatest impact of COVID-19: Project 37 used multiple data tools including GIS, COVID-19 case and mortality rates, and the social vulnerability index (SVI) to identify communities in which to focus their intervention (see Figure 2). This team identified community-based health care partners in counties with high COVID-19 case rates and exhibiting high social vulnerability: Essex, Passaic, Middlesex, and Union.

Figure 2: NJ HEROES TOO Counties of Focus displaying racial/ethnic density, poverty and coverage of health organization and community partners

Note: figure reproduced from Project 37's grant application.

Create open and bidirectional communication to engage communities effectively: Project 37 worked with community and health care organizations to host community conversations to gauge community attitudes about the pandemic and to better understand their resource needs. One important communication gap that became a recurrent theme as vaccines became increasingly available prior to the advent of the Omicron variant was the question of “Is testing relevant?” In response, Project 37 collaborated with community partners to host a series of virtual conversations in the format of town halls to bring in academic and non-academic experts to talk through the science of testing and communicate the benefits of testing and its importance. Through continued conversations about testing and the study findings as well as involving their partners as co-authors in knowledge creation, Project 37 leveraged existing trusted relationships and created new ones between their researchers, stakeholders, advocates, and partners.

Incorporate cross-sector partnerships to foster different perspectives: Project 37 began with a core of 16 partnered groups and expanded the breadth and scope of community partners by applying a snowball outreach technique to engage a total of 22 partners. The six-person interdisciplinary multiple principle investigator leadership team of Project 37 includes three publicly engaged researchers (a sociologist, a pediatrician, and an urban health educator) with expertise in community-engaged scholarship who have deep-rooted and longstanding relationships with both health care and community stakeholders and groups. They were joined by three cohort and clinical trial researchers (an epidemiologist, an immunologist, and a pulmonologist). Together, the team was able to leverage the strengths of their different disciplines and the expert knowledge of their citizen scientist stakeholder collaborators to think creatively about how best to engage the community in problem solving.

Use participatory and sustainable budgeting practices for all partners: Interviewees noted community partner engagement was a key strength of this project. Funding was allocated to support knowledge co-creation (i.e., understanding the core concerns and creating messaging and media content that addressed those concerns). Each partner was included in the project budget. Community partners were given flexibility to use their funding to best

serve their individual constituents. Additional funding supported a media consulting group who helped to develop a unified dissemination platform. Interviewees expressed that future public health policies should be designed to support longitudinal community engagement and management and build resilience in communities.

Project 48: Adapting Community-Based Task-Shifting for the COVID-19 Response Among Underserved Populations in Piedmont, North Carolina (ACT-UP)

Partners: University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill, Hispanic Liaison, Piedmont Health Services, General Baptist State Convention of North Carolina

Project 48 is focused on community-based task shifting and partnerships with trained non-clinical health workers. The team also supports Piedmont Health Services, a network of Federally Qualified Health Centers (FQHCs), to provide COVID-19 testing and vaccination services to communities. This model adapts a proven implementation strategy from the global HIV response to disseminate COVID-19 information and reach communities with COVID-19 testing and vaccine services.¹⁰² Key strategies include:

Fill operational gaps with strategic partnerships and coalition-building: Often, community-based organizations lack the resources and infrastructure to run testing clinics while health providers fail to meaningfully engage communities historically excluded and impacted by structural disadvantages in the health care system. Project 48 has bridged clinical expertise and logistical infrastructure by building a coalition of partners to provide health education and conduct outreach, testing, and vaccination. Piedmont Health and state and local health departments implemented testing (and later vaccination) clinics while working with community partners such as Hispanic Liaison, SER Hispano, and faith-based organizations such as those within the General Baptist State Convention of North Carolina. The cross-sector partnerships provided community partners with operational support to bring health care services to people and data to prioritize and plan innovative interventions.

Allocate funding resources specifically for CHWs to overcome anticipated and pre-existing staffing constraints:

Project 48 has provided operational support to bring health care services to people and data to prioritize and plan innovative interventions. Specifically, Project 48 included funding for staff at Piedmont Health, including CHWs and leadership staff who could specifically focus on COVID-19 services, to facilitate task shifting and task sharing across the team.

Connect health services to the population through community liaisons:

Faith-based organizations and advocacy groups (e.g., Hispanic Liaison) helped remove barriers between the community and health system that make accessing health care inconvenient, costly, and complicated. For example, Hispanic Liaison worked with community members to set up testing appointments and eliminated complicated technology and language barriers posed by lengthy online registration sites. Instead, Hispanic Liaison connected with community members over the phone and in person to fill out registration forms on their behalf.

Develop protocols that are amendable to real-time changes and challenges:

In late September 2021, Project 48 recognized a new challenge to the vaccination process – people were misplacing or losing their vaccination cards. To solve this problem, project leaders developed a communication process to remind people of the importance of (and provide strategies for) keeping their vaccine cards safe. The communications team created flyers (available online and in print) in Spanish and English for health care providers and trusted community partners to remind people what to do after vaccination and how to store their cards.

Project 56: Alive Church Network: Increasing COVID-19 Testing in Chicago's African American Testing Deserts

Partners: Rush University Medical Center, University of Illinois Chicago, Alive Church Network, Hope Community Church, Greater Rock MB Church, Cook County Department of Public Health

Project 56 worked with local churches to establish COVID-19 testing sites in Black communities in Chicago that have experienced limited testing availability, contributing to racial disparities in health outcomes from the outset of the pandemic.¹⁰³ Project 56 focused on outreach and information sharing to overcome challenges related to misinformation and rapidly changing COVID-19 guidance. Key strategies include:

Partner with established community organizations, including churches, to select community-based testing sites:

Project 56 partnered with church pastors and teams of community members to create the necessary infrastructure to provide accessible testing. Churches also offered physical locations for testing sites to be housed in areas with high COVID-19 positivity rates. As COVID-19 vaccines became available, these church-based testing sites also became important vaccine distribution locations. Some community members reported only getting vaccinated because their churches and trusted community organizations were promoting and providing the vaccine.

Co-locate public health interventions with other community services and events:

Testing efforts were more successful at locations that provided other social supports and community services such as food assistance and financial aid. Examples of sites included back-to-school events and youth baseball league games in the Park District.

Address CHW shortages through long-term employment models:

Although funding for testing sites was made available, the pandemic resulted in staffing shortages. To establish and retain long-term community relationships, Rush University Medical Center hired CHWs directly as employees, rather than contracting on a month-to-month basis. This funding strategy helped ensure the availability

of team members to keep church-based testing and vaccination sites open, as well as facilitate trust and open communication with community members. Future public health community interventions should likewise create sustainable payment models to prevent health care staffing shortages during periods of emergency or increased health care demand.

Allocate research and implementation funding to maintain community partner relationships: Interviewees from Project 56 noted the collaborative team of clinicians, CHWs, and community partners as a key success factor. RADx-UP funding allowed Project 56 to establish an academic-community partnership based on existing networks within the community they serve.

Project 62: Social, Ethical, and Behavioral Implications Research on COVID-19 Testing and Vaccine Uptake among Rural Latino Migrants in Southwest Florida

Partners: Hispanic Services Council, University of South Florida Latino Alliance, Local FQHCs

Project 62 aims to develop and implement integrated community-based prevention marketing strategies, informed by community members' perspectives, to promote uptake of COVID-19 testing and vaccination. In collaboration with their community partner the Hispanic Services Council (HSC), Project 62 focused on engaging rural Latinx migrant and immigrant communities in southwest Florida to elicit community perceptions of COVID-19 as well as feedback on culturally tailored marketing and education approaches. Key strategies include:

Provide adequate funding for community partners: Given that many community-based organizations are often underfunded and resource-constrained, Project 62 designed its grant structure to provide funding directly to the HSC to use as needed for the project. Adequate funding was achieved in part by RADx-UP's encouragement of equal partnerships between academic institutions and community organizations. As a result, the HSC was afforded a stable budget for their involvement in Project

62 that allowed them to assume a lead role in study activities and hire local study staff. For example, the HSC led community workshops and presentations, contributed to survey question development, co-authored conference abstracts, and are co-authoring manuscripts that are in progress. Interviewees felt the equitable collaboration between the HSC and the University of South Florida (USF) increased the richness of their research project.

Invest in local CHWs: The HSC provides health education and community support to over 5000 Latinx community members through their *promotora* program. Promotoras from local rural Latinx communities identified by Project 62 were key to enrolling and engaging participants in focus group discussions and surveys. Interviewees noted difficulty recruiting and retaining promotoras due to issues related to COVID-19, compensation, and lack of benefits with part-time positions; however, the HSC's dedication to the professional development of promotoras helped to overcome these issues. For instance, HSC helped promotoras revise their resumes and provided training certificates (e.g., Collaborative Institutional Training Initiative certification) that could help them obtain future work.

Develop and implement communication strategies in collaboration with communities: Using findings from their focus groups and surveys, Project 62 will collaboratively (HSC Director, USF marketing and research investigators, and promotoras) develop integrated marketing strategies to produce culturally tailored communication materials, media campaigns, and HSC community-based programs to increase COVID-19 testing and vaccine uptake. To illustrate this, interviewees described how preliminary analyses of survey data are helping them to determine ways to frame COVID-19 messaging and groups to direct resources and services. Feedback on the formulated social marketing products will be obtained through group *charlas*, or community discussion groups facilitated by promotoras and USF research staff.